

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF WATER PURIFICATION BY OZONATION

Bokanova A.,*Professor of the, d.t.s.***Yermakhanova F.,***Ass. professor, c.t.s.***Abseitov E.,***Ass. professor, c.t.s.***Ramazanova D.,***graduate student**Transport and Energy Faculty,**Eurasian National University by name L.N. Gumilev,**Astana, Kazakhstan Republic***Issabekov Zh.***Dean of the Naturel sciences Faculty, PhD,**Internation Kazak-Turk University by name Achmet Yasay***Abstract**

The modern problem of providing the population with clean and safe drinking water remains one of the most important in the world. The article is a study on the use of ozonation in the process of drinking water treatment in order to improve the quality and safety of water supply. The relevance of this topic is associated with several important aspects, such as providing the population with clean drinking water, pollution of water resources, public health, and technological progress. Ozonation is an advanced technology used to remove contaminants, microorganisms and organic compounds from water, making it safe for consumption. The article analyzes the various aspects of ozonation shown in tables and figures, the benefits, efficiency of this process and its impact on water quality. Particular attention is paid to removing bacteria, viruses and other pathogens from water, which is important for public health. The authors offer developed technological schemes, as well as their small-sized devices based on corona discharge from 100 micron microwires, tests of which show that ozonation can significantly improve the quality of drinking water, reduce the content of organic pollutants, as well as eliminate odors and provide tastes. The effectiveness of ozonation also depends on various parameters such as ozone dosage, contact time and water pH.

This article also contains drinking water quality standards, providing readers not only with information about ozonation technology, but also with regulatory context. This is especially important for assessing whether water meets safety and quality standards. Based on the results presented in the article, conclusions were drawn.

This article provides important information for water and public health professionals and those interested in the technological aspects of drinking water treatment. She emphasizes the importance of ozonation as a modern and effective method of disinfection and water purification.

Keywords: drinking water, quality, water purification, ozonation, ozonation technology.

Introduction. Water is the source of life, and its significant importance for the health and well-being of mankind cannot be overestimated. "The introduction of water-saving technologies is a very important issue that requires urgent measures. In addition, now we cannot do without a new tariff policy that corresponds to the current reality" [1]. Water is the source of life, and its critical importance for the health and well-being of mankind cannot be overestimated. However, despite its abundance on the surface of our planet, access to clean and safe drinking water remains a problem for millions of people around the world. According to the data provided in the UN Report on the state of the World's water resources, wastewater discharge annually pollutes about 12 thousand km³ of water. Polluted water is a source of mass diseases, increased mortality, especially among children, and also causes an increase in social tension [1-3]. If pollution continues at the same pace as population growth, the planet will lose 18 thousand km³ of fresh water by 2050. About 900 km³/year of industrial and domestic wastewater is discharged into the hydrosphere annually, about 10 billion tons. tons of oil and petroleum products. The use of chemicals in the

form of mineral fertilizers to increase soil fertility has led to massive water pollution. The removal of organic substances into the ocean is estimated at 300-380 million tons per year. The scale of water pollution is such that about 2 million tons of water containing industrial waste, chemicals, and fertilizers are discharged into reservoirs around the world every day. Scientists all over the world pay attention to the assessment of water compliance with safety and quality standards [1-3].

Research methods. When writing the article, various general scientific methods were used, which represent a systematic approach to the study and analysis of the ozonation process in the context of purification and disinfection of drinking water. The study used literature sources and experimental methods that allowed us to draw conclusions about the technological effectiveness of ozonation for purification and disinfection of drinking water.

The article used materials from domestic and foreign scientists analyzing pollution of natural and drinking water from decentralized water supply systems. The

main types of pollution are mineral and organic substances, harmful gases, pathogens. The basic material was the standards of the Republic of Kazakhstan [2-3].

GOST 2874-82 "Drinking water. Hygienic requirements and quality control" applied. According to it-before entering the network, water is monitored for microbiological, chemical and organoleptic indicators.

Results and discussion. Pollution of natural waters also affects the quality of drinking water obtained from non-centralized water supply systems. The authors' devices were used in the experiments (table 1) [4, p.233].

Table 1

N	Type	Volt., V	Frequen., Hz	Pover, W	Produce, dm ³	Time, min	Weight, kg	Dimensions, mm
1	Okbr1	220	50	40	3	20	10	800*400
2	Okbr2	220	50	100	5	120	52	715x700

Microbes, bacteria, parasites, the presence of which leads to infectious diseases and others (table 2) [2-5, p.18]. The chemical components in Table 3.

Table 2

The name of the indicator	The standard	After ozonation	Metod
The number of microorganisms in cm ³ of water	100	65	GOST 18963
The number of E. coli bacteria in dm ³ of water (Coli-index)	3	0	GOST 18963

Table 3

The name of the indicator	The standard	After ozonation	Metod
Aluminum (Al), mg/dm ³	0,5	0,1	GOST 18165
Molybdenum (Mo), mg/dm ³	0,25	0	GOST 18308
Arsenic (As), mg/dm ³	0,05	0	GOST 4152
Nitrates (NO ₂), mg/dm ³	45,0	5	GOST 18826
Plumbum (Pb), mg/dm ³	0,03	0	GOST 18293
Selenium (Se), mg/dm ³	0,01	0	GOST 19413
Fluoride by regions of RK (F), mg/dm ³ : I и II	1,6	0,3	
III	1,2		
IV	0,7		

Currently, in a number of regions of the country, the state of drinking water supply can have an adverse effect on the health of the population [5, p.18].

With all the variety of substances in drinking water (the Sanitary and Epidemiological Service has es-

tablished more than 2000 standards. The most characteristic groups of pollutants for water supply sources can be identified: Fe, Mn, Pl, Cu, Cl.

Table 4-5 shows the indicators of substances that affect the organoleptic properties of water.

The organoleptic properties of the water must comply with the requirements specified in Table 4.

Table 4

The name of the indicator	The standard	After ozonation	Metod
pH	6,0 – 9,0	8,0	It is measured on the pH meter of any model
Ferrum (Fe) mg/dm ³	0,3	0,03	GOST 4031
Rigidity, моль/м ³	7,0	2,1	GOST 4151
Manganese (Mn), mg/dm ³	0,1	0	GOST 4974
Cuprum (Cu ²⁺), mg/dm ³	1,0	0,3	GOST 4388
Polyphosphates (PO ₄ ³⁻), mg/dm ³	3,5	2,0	GOST 18309
Sulfates (SO ₄), mg/dm ³	500	200	GOST 4389
Dry residue, mg/dm ³	1000	350	GOST 18164
Chlorides (Cl ⁻), mg/dm ³	350	65	GOST 4245
Zinc (Zn ²⁺), mg/dm ³	5,0	0,6	GOST 18293

A small ozonation substation consists of one element. Ozone is obtained on the basis of a corona discharge on 100mk wires [6]. The power consumption of electricity is 40 watts. Figure 1 shows the power supply scheme of the ozonator installation [7, 289 -8, p.403].

The mixing of purified water with ozonated air can be carried out in various ways: bubbling water through filters, perforated (porous) pipes, mixing with ejectors, agitators, etc. [9-10, p.190].

Figure 1 – Diagram of a small ozonator substation

1 –compressor; 2 –step-up transformer; 3 –ozonator; 4 –contact column; 5 –porous tubes; 6 – pipe for air; 7 –pipe with purified water; 8 –tank of purified water; 9 –pipe for supplying air to the ozonator; 10 –pipe for supplying ozone-air mixture into the contact column; 11 –solar panel

After water purification, the exhaust gases are released into the atmosphere.

Conclusion.

As a result of the use of ozone in water, the concentration of heavy metals has been reduced, as well as the color and taste have been improved [11, p.35].

Figure 2 – Reduction of iron in water before and after ozonation

Figure 2 shows the effectiveness of water purification from iron. The analysis of water samples for iron content was performed in the Kazecoanalyse laboratory [12, p.35-13, p.81].

Ozone, as an environmentally sound purifier, can be used as an effective means for water treatment in water supply systems, wastewater treatment and gas emissions into the atmosphere [5, p.18]. The experiments were performed on the okbr1 apparatus.

Table 5

Organoleptic parameters of water			
The name of the indicator	The standard	After ozonation	Metod
Odor at 200 ° C and when heated to 600 ° C, points	2	0,3	GOST 3351
Taste and aftertaste at 200 ° C, points	2	0,1	GOST 3351
Colour, degree C ⁰	20	3	GOST 3351
Turbidity, mg/dm ³	1,5	0	GOST 3351

Figure 3 – Reduction of sulfates in water before and after ozonation

Figure 3 shows that during ozonation, the amount of sulfates reaches the norm in 9.5 minutes. The reduction of sulfates in water to 200 mg/dm³ occurs with an increase in time to 11.5 minutes. This indicates the effect of the method of ozonation.

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